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Effect of Shared Leadership on Team Effectiveness in School Administration of Harvarde College of Science Business and Management Studies, Abeokuta, Ogun State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT:

This study was descriptive research which was based on the opinion of team leaders and team members. This study examined the effect of shared leadership on team effectiveness in school administration. Shared leadership has been defined as a dynamic, interactive influence process among group members with the aim of guiding one another toward the accomplishment of group, organisational, or both goals. The samples of this research were 34 respondents; which comprised of the principal officers, administration heads, faculty heads, and departmental heads in Harvarde College of Science Business and Management Studies, Abeokuta, Ogun Sate, Nigeria.. These respondents and the schools were selected using purposive sampling technique, a non-probability sampling technique. The respondents included the Provost, Deputy Provost, Registrar, Deputy Registrar, Bursar, School Administrator, Administrative Officers, Admission Officers, Examination and Record Officer, The Deans, and The Head of Departments. The responses of the respondents show that shared leadership is practised in the general school administration of Harvarde College of Science Business and Management Studies, Ogun State, Nigeria, as well as among teams within the school, which is the focus of this research's study in the area of school administration.

KEYWORDS:

Shared Leadership, Team Effectiveness, Team Trust, Team Commitment, Nigeria

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Introduction

Shared leadership is the practice of delegating authority while maintaining a single point of control. The performance of an organisation is improved through shared leadership. Shared leadership can be established through being open, encouraging autonomy, and being attentive to other people's viewpoints. Shared leadership, as defined by Bergman, Rentsch, Small, Davenport & Bergman (2012), occurs when two or more team members assume the position of team leader in an effort to guide and influence other team members in order to improve team effectiveness.

Given that many businesses have been influenced by social media and more recent online technologies and have started to facilitate the exchange of information, business management is quickly shifting from outdated, authoritarian models to more open ones. In the 21st century and the age of high technology, nothing is more important than having a diverse pool of knowledge and talent to draw from when merging, restructuring, expanding, and managing daily business operations. The more adaptable the leadership model you use, the more equipped your business will be to handle a variety of situations. Using a shared leadership model enables everyone in a company to work toward a common objective by integrating their knowledge, thinking, and creativity, according to various research on the importance of shared leadership above the traditional leadership of superior to subordinate. Simply expressed, shared leadership is when two or more team members take on the role of team leader in an effort to influence and guide team members in order to maximize team effectiveness.

The behaviour of an individual and their relationship to their followers has historically been used to describe leadership in all contexts. This has led to a focus on the behaviour, traits, and activities of leaders in both training and academia. The high-tech, quick-changing environment that defines the 21st century will force successful organizations to depend more and more on highly independent, knowledgeable people who collaborate in multidisciplinary teams. In light of this, shared leadership can be characterized as a team-wide endeavour that supports this manner of operating. Alternatively, shared leadership can be described as a dynamic, interactive influencing process among group members with the aim of guiding one another toward the accomplishment of group, organizational, or both goals. The idea of shared leadership presents leadership as an active collective effort. It does not depend on top-down control but is multidirectional and cooperative. Every participant has the ability to influence ongoing organizational transformation, from conception to execution. People at all levels of a company can adopt the shared leadership concept.

"The digital revolution is creating an entirely other management model where the presumption is that the smartest organizations have instant access to the collective knowledge of the company," writes Rod Collins, author of *Leadership in a Wiki World* (Dog Ear Publishing, June 2010). With shared leadership, everyone is given the opportunity to lead in the capacity in which they are most skilled. It essentially takes a collective approach to responsibility sharing. It promotes group decision-making with an emphasis on ongoing growth and progress and is in part based on trust. Experts may be divided into teams with team leaders (two or more members may be the influencers), spreading power and authority rather than relying on a single function to lead. Each person's knowledge can be utilized, giving them a chance to highlight their unique skills.

The strongest instances of shared leadership, according to Greg A. Chung-Yan, professor in the Department of Psychology at the University of Windsor in Ontario, are when decision-making is

distributed among several people. Anyone who takes the time to think about the issues facing businesses in the twenty-first century will realize that things change too quickly for one person to know how to react. Any event might have a number of causes, and it takes a variety of viewpoints to fully comprehend its significance and determine the best course of action. The long-term success of businesses depends on having a pipeline of potential leaders. It makes sense that businesses today are drawn to the advantages of shared leadership rather than leadership that is focused in a single charismatic person. Whatever the name or specifics of the organizational structure, the times appear to demand leaders who can be first among equals. Delegation is not all that this is. It has to do with a team having a shared sense of mission and ownership over the overall direction of the business. The team's work may be led by many individuals in different capacities, but everyone is always in charge.

Shared leadership is defined as "broadly sharing power and influence among a set of individuals rather than centralizing it in the hands of a single individual who acts in the clear role of a dominant superior," according to a study published in the *International Journal of Artificial Intelligence and Agent Technology*. Compared to the conventional vertical hierarchical management style, shared leadership is different. In a vertical management structure, people in management jobs make the majority of the decisions, while those in inferior posts have minimal influence over those decisions. Shared leadership involves more cooperation. Even if there is still just one person in command, there is sharing of authority and influence. This could imply that people have greater discretion over decisions affecting their jobs or that there is more of an open-door approach where everyone's opinions are taken into account.

Declan Fitzsimons states in the 2016 issue of the *Harvard Business Review* that shared leadership improves organizational performance. A company's operations are positively impacted by shared leadership. This philosophy appreciates and promotes individual initiative. Employee productivity and job satisfaction both rise when they feel empowered to take action on what they know needs to be done rather than waiting to be told what to do. People have a greater drive for success when they feel like they have an impact on the organization, that they have some authority, and that they have some responsibility. People work harder on everything they are personally committed in because goals become more personal to them.

In the Roman Empire, a group of people shared authority through the Senate, establishing the earliest foundations of shared leadership. However, organizational efforts to manage people in teams and a focus on self-leadership, whereby people "lead others to lead themselves," led to the concept of sharing power and influence among a number of people emerging (Cox & Sims, 1996).

As opposed to the idea of a team being led by a singular leader, shared leadership refers to how team members influence one another and share responsibility for tasks. This makes it necessary to distinguish shared leadership from team leadership. When a group of people work together to lead each other to achievement, it is called shared leadership (Carson, Tesluk, & Marrone, 2007). The fact that the influence process encompasses more than simply the downward effect of subordinates by a positional leader is a major contrast between shared and traditional models of leadership. Instead than being concentrated in the hands of one person acting as the leader, leadership is spread among a group of people (Pearce and Conger, 2002: 1-3). In order to distribute or share the responsibility of leadership within the team in response to each situation and problem being addressed, the team values each member's unique experience, expertise, and capacity. Teams and leaders must be aware of and

understand the characteristics of a strong team since weak or inefficient teams can be annoying and potentially poisonous. The organizational unit inside today's organization that is increasing at the highest rate is the multidisciplinary team. One person or one discipline can no longer possess the knowledge and experience necessary to address the complexity of today's situations. To find a solution to the complex issue of global warming, for instance, governments must make sure that scientists, engineers, geographers, meteorologists, biologists, botanists, oceanographers, doctors, computer programmers, ecologists, and manufacturers all contribute their specialized knowledge and experience. Instead of one profession working alone, the breakthroughs are more likely to result from the interplay between all the other disciplines.

Recent studies on change management teams, virtual teams, and new start-up teams have shown that leadership should be shared among team members rather than being vested in a single person. These studies have used quantitative techniques to show that shared leadership can and does improve organizational performance. Anyone who has attempted to divide the responsibilities and rights of leadership among their teams is likely aware of how difficult this task can be.

Changing to shared leadership alters relationships between team members and changes how choices are made. Executive VPs may like having the power to manage the entire company, but they will struggle to manage one another. They may be reluctant to accept and use the authority to hold each other accountable for the performance of their function or business unit because they are accustomed to reporting directly to you. They might agree to stop berating one another while they wait for you to intervene. Unless you make it obvious that they must support and challenge each other rather than performing the former only, this will force you into the role of the messenger of bad news.

The discomfort of these new relationships can be handled by groups in a few different ways, each of which has its own dysfunctions. The first is for team members to divide into smaller groups and speak mostly with people they already feel at ease with, ignoring or undermining the others. The second is to single out a specific person or group of people and blame them for all delays and problems. Though HR and IT are popular choices, anyone could be chosen. Joining in is the worst thing you can do. It is your responsibility to determine when creating subgroups is a constructive strategy to divide the team's workload and when it is a detrimental way to sidestep contentious problems. When a team member or group seems to be performing below average, it's important to determine how much the scapegoat actually isn't up to standard and how much the team is just using their incompetence as an excuse to feel superior.

Considering all of these factors together, this study aims to improve our knowledge of the mechanisms behind shared leadership and explores whether it is associated with improved team performance in higher educational setting. Teams make up schools, and when these teams collaborate, they form the larger team that is the school as a whole. While it has been noted that teachers are generally viewed as being stereotypical because they like to work alone, secluded in their classrooms, they are now starting to embrace working inside a team—at least within a great team.

Statement of the Problem

Recent leadership studies have revealed that the administration of businesses is quickly shifting from outdated, authoritarian models to more flexible ones, one of which is shared leadership. In these high-tech times, nothing is more important than having a wide range of knowledge and

expertise to draw from when it comes to combining, restructuring, expanding, and managing day-to-day business activities. Educational sector is not exempted from this leadership system which encourages autonomy participation in decision making, collaboration, supportive group climate and exchange of diverse ideas. However, so far leadership researches have paid little attention to the use of shared leadership in educational sector. Hence, this research work intends to examine *whether* shared leadership is positively related to team effectiveness in the Higher Educational system, specifically at the Harvarde College of Science Business and Management Studies, Abeokuta, Ogun Sate, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions have been raised:

1. Is shared leadership adopted?
2. Is there any relationship between shared leadership and team effectiveness?
3. Is there any relationship between shared leadership and team trust?
4. Does shared leadership enhance team commitment?

Hypothesis

The following hypothesis were raised in the study:

1. Shared leadership is not adopted Harvarde College of Science Business and Management Studies, Abeokuta, Ogun State, Nigeria.
2. There is no relationship between shared leadership and team effectiveness
3. There is no relationship between shared leadership and team trust

Review

Concept of Shared Leadership

Gaining a competitive edge and fostering employee happiness depend heavily on leadership. Organizational structures were vertically organized for a long time, with the formal leader being positioned above the followers in the hierarchical framework. According to this idea, leadership is a downward process in which the formal leader of a team or organization influences his or her subordinates (Pearce and Conger, 2003; Bass and Bass, 2008). However, since the turn of the millennium, businesses have had to deal with rapidly shifting surroundings and rising workloads that include complex activities (Day et al., 2004). These modifications put unwarranted demands on formal leaders, as it is doubtful that one individual can successfully carry out all leadership duties (Yukl, 2010).

Organizations have consequently begun to seriously consider alternatives to the traditional single-leader model. This discussion gave rise to a shared leadership strategy, which contends that it is more practical and efficient to rely on the skills of the team members to share these leadership responsibilities rather than placing all the responsibility on one person. "An emergent team property that comes from the distribution of leadership influence across many team members" is how shared leadership is defined (Carson et al., 2007, p. 1218). According to this strategy, leaders cannot simply be formally appointed to their position and given explicit, official authority over it (e.g., managers and directors). Instead, because of their regular encounters with their subordinates, leaders can also become unofficial leaders (Pearce and Conger, 2003).

Sharing duties with team members is one way formal leaders can manage the multitude of obligations that come with their position (i.e., shared leadership). Business management, including management in education, is transitioning quickly from outdated, authoritarian paradigms to more open practices. These shifts were motivated by social media and more recent online technologies that encourage information sharing as businesses look for new avenues for innovation and expansion. The interest in shared leadership has grown significantly over the past ten years, and performance psychology has given the topic significant attention. In fact, studies of organizational teams have shown that shared leadership has an advantage over vertical leadership structures in a number of areas, including goal commitment, team confidence, and observable performance measures like productivity (e.g., Hoch, 2007; Parker et al., 2015).

Shared responsibilities have a beneficial effect because they encourage the sharing of values and norms and create a greater sense of team competence, according to literature in particular concentrating on contemporary shared leadership structures in businesses, such as self-directed and agile teams (Solansky, 2008; McIntyre and Foti, 2013). Furthermore, it has been discovered that shared leadership acts as a buffer against team conflict (e.g., Bergman et al., 2012).

Sharing power and influence while keeping one person in control, is known as shared leadership. Transparency, promoting autonomy, and being receptive to other people's views all help to establish shared leadership. One definition of shared leadership is "broadly sharing power and influence among a set of individuals, rather than concentrating it in the hands of a single individual who acts in the clear role of a dominant superior." This definition comes from a joint research study that was published in the International Journal of Artificial Intelligence and Agent Technology.

The idea of shared leadership presents leadership as an active collective effort. It does not depend on top-down control but is multidirectional and cooperative. Every participant has the ability to influence ongoing organizational transformation, from conception to execution. People at all levels of a company can adopt the shared leadership concept. With shared leadership, everyone is given the opportunity to lead in the capacity in which they are most skilled. It essentially takes a collective approach to responsibility sharing. It promotes group decision-making with an emphasis on ongoing growth and progress and is in part based on trust. Experts may be divided into teams with team leaders (two or more members may be the influencers), spreading power and authority rather than relying on a single function to lead. Each person's knowledge can be utilized, giving them a chance to highlight their unique skills.

The Research Conceptual Model

Characteristics of Shared Leadership

The shared leadership approach emphasizes the notion that works are shared through a team setting that depends on (Carson, 2007). The cornerstones of shared leadership are these three facets.

- A shared purpose,
- Social support, and
- Voice.

Shared purpose: Understand and appreciate collective goals

By developing a sense of shared purpose, team members make sure that everyone is aware of and supportive of the primary goals of the team project.

Social support: Provide emotional support to each other:

In order to provide social support, team members must encourage one another or acknowledge each team member's unique contributions.

Social support: Offer emotional support to one another

Voice: Appreciate each team member's contribution

The capacity of each team member to contribute to the team's process is the final tenet of voice. When a team values and prioritizes each member's contribution, voice occurs (Carson et al., 2007).

Comparison of Shared Leadership and Traditional Leadership

Compared to the conventional vertical hierarchical management style, shared leadership is different. In a vertical management structure, people in management jobs make the majority of the decisions, while those in inferior posts have minimal influence over those decisions.

Shared leadership involves more cooperation. Even if there is still just one person in command, there is sharing of authority and influence. This could imply that people have more discretion over decisions affecting their jobs or that there is an open-door policy where everyone's opinions are fairly considered.

Comparison of Shared leadership and Team leadership

If there are teams in existence, many individuals believe they have shared leadership. While the hierarchy is broken down, shared leadership isn't really achieved. There is often still a team leader within a team; but, in the absence of a team leader, the shared power only applies to the team and not to the organization as a whole.

However, when creating a company culture, teams might be a fantastic way to introduce shared leadership. Teams provide more manageable spaces and can help workers get experience in a leadership role. A study published in the *Academy of Management Journal* found that for shared leadership to be effective, the team must already have a strong sense of camaraderie, clear goals, and a culture of support for one another.

Comparison of Shared Leadership and Traditional Leadership in School Management

The principal is ultimately responsible for everything that happens in the school—from staff and student safety, to the operation and maintenance of the physical plant, to student achievement. How, then, can a principal share leadership, and what are the benefits and drawbacks? First, for those unfamiliar with the concept, here is a comparison—including a few of the potential differences—

between shared leadership and the ways in which most principals work with a traditional leadership team (see Table 1 in Appendix I):

Role Differentiation in Shared Leadership

A clear definition and distribution of roles has been said to be crucial to the effectiveness of a shared leadership system (Bray and Brawley, 2002). The team structure is most frequently employed. It was discovered that a team structure with both an expressive and an instrumental leader reduced time, effort, and psychological tensions between team members (Pearce and Conger, 2003). In addition to these well-established recommendations on various leadership responsibilities, numerous other studies have shown that differentiating roles within an organizational team improves the team's effectiveness (Lee et al., 2015). It should be noted, nevertheless, that the majority of research on role differentiation has only ever centered on the duties of formal leaders (e.g., Kozlowski and Bell, 2013). Despite repeated requests from academics in the field to establish leadership positions for peer leaders inside organizational teams (e.g., Lee et al., 2015), there is currently a dearth of such a set of leadership roles for team members.

Importance of shared leadership

Nothing is more important when merging, restructuring, growing, and managing daily business operations than having a wide range of knowledge and skills at your disposal. The more adaptable your leadership model is, the better equipped your business will be to tackle a variety of problems. By combining their knowledge, ideas, and creativity, everyone in your organization may work toward a single objective by using a shared leadership approach. A Harvard Business Review article claims that shared leadership improves corporate performance as a whole. Shared leadership fosters and promotes individual initiative, which has a good impact on how a firm runs. Employee productivity and job satisfaction rise when they have the freedom to take action on what they know needs to be done rather of waiting to be told.

Additionally, a happy workforce creates a more conducive environment for the operation of the business. People have a greater motivation for success when they feel like they have an impact on the organization, have some power, and are responsible for something. People naturally work harder at something they are personally committed in because goals become more personal to them. Simply defined, when decision-making is distributed across several people that is when shared leadership is best demonstrated. Due to their capacity for quick responses and rapid adaptation to changing conditions, it is said that organizations with this kind of structure are better able to maintain their competitiveness. 2016 (Northouse) additionally, shared leadership improves businesses' performance, increases their efficiency, and benefits teams by reducing conflict and fostering greater cohesion and trust. It is also believed that when organizational leadership is used in businesses, this shared team notion becomes the secret to their success.

Even the strongest leaders require assistance with making decisions, which is another factor supporting the value of shared leadership. It seems uncommon for organizational leaders to be fully qualified to make all decisions. The idea of shared leadership is essential to a functional company because of this. The complexity and ambiguity that teams frequently face, according to Carson et al. (2007), make it improbable that a single external leader can successfully carry out all necessary leadership functions. (pg. 1217) Many employees, especially those with advanced knowledge and skills, aspire for autonomy in their work. These workers aim to provide this knowledge and talent for

the benefit of the group. These team members "want to have more influence over and involvement in the leadership roles of their teams" (Carson et. al 2007). It is advantageous for the team bonding as well as the autonomy of the team members. "Teams with shared leadership had less conflict, more consensus, more trust, and more coherence than teams without shared leadership," according to research (Northouse, 2016, pg. 365).

Because of the many benefits that were previously outlined, shared leadership is a notion that organizations may employ to their advantage. There are additional advantages as well, according to Carson et al. (2007), who wrote that "shared leadership can provide organizations with competitive advantage through increases in commitment, in the personal and organizational resources brought to bear on complex tasks, in openness to reciprocal influence from others, and in the sharing of information" (pg. 1217). These justifications give specifics on why, in my opinion, the team concept of shared leadership is the secret to the efficiency of every high-quality organization.

The shortcomings of shared leadership

In general, studies on shared leadership have shown that it has favorable effects on both team and individual outcomes. There aren't many studies that examine shared leadership's drawbacks. One or more of shared leadership's reported drawbacks include the following:

1. **Slow Decision Making:** As decision-making is a collaborative process, it may take groups longer time to reach choices than it would under traditional leadership. The development of relationships and communication between team members require more time, but these decisions typically have better results than hasty ones.
2. **Peer Attitude:** Another drawback of implementing shared leadership in an organization, particularly a school, is the response of other staff members who are not designated team leaders or given leadership responsibilities. There is a taboo in our field against one instructor elevating themselves over the others, according to Roland Barth's (2013) writing. You may see it in talks about merit pay, but you can also see it when one teacher takes ownership of a situation at the school while the other instructors are only thinking about their own 30 students. Teachers will discipline any teacher who assumes a leadership position.

Reasons Leaders Should Adopt a Shared Leadership Model

1. **Joint decisions are wiser decisions:** More people being involved in the decision-making process generally results in better results. This is due to the fact that people frequently aren't aware of the underlying biases that affect their judgment and thought processes. True accountability is also built on shared leadership, whether the results are favorable or unfavorable. Being held responsible for outcomes that they have no control over is unfair, counterproductive, and certain to cause conflict and resentment.
2. **Sharing Power Builds Trust:** Co-leadership boosts respect and loyalty, which in turn fosters healthy, low-conflict relationships. This is because people feel capable and trusted when a leader gives them authority. Through shared leadership activities, a leader can show that they value what their team members have to say and are somewhat humble by asking for their ideas and advice. In contrast to an arrogant "know-it-all" who won't accept any dissent or criticism, leaders who are prepared to confess they don't know everything are much more likely to win their employees' trust and support.
3. **Including Others Helps Them Develop Leadership Skills:** Planning for succession will fail if power is not shared! People come and go, but wise companies always have a solid strategy

in place to replace their essential personnel. However, such a strategy must guarantee that people being prepared for increased responsibility are given the chance to develop the abilities required for shared leadership and advance by taking on more responsibility. Leaders can play a mentoring role by giving high-potential employees the authority to make decisions, better preparing them for their upcoming positions as leaders.

4. **Sharing Responsibility Equals Sharing Power:** Power-loving leaders actually establish self-support networks for themselves. These leaders profit by relying on their team while being certain that the task will be completed rather than acting as "lone rangers." Leaders can rely on their team to "have their back" without fail since they have invested in their growth and are always accessible to offer advice when necessary.
5. **Shared Leadership in School Administration:** In order to create organizational cultures that encourage, nourish, and support leadership and leaders, Duignan et al. (2003 - SOLR Project) argue that there must be a significant change in the definition, perspective, and scope (depth and breadth) of leadership in schools. Building a Culture of Shared Leadership in an Organization is how they describe this development. Many educational leaders—particularly principals—find themselves alone and alone because they feel that they are ultimately in charge of providing leadership in their respective schools. Such an attitude reflects a very constrained understanding of leadership. Principals, in particular, must feel confident enough in themselves to freely delegate leadership responsibilities to teachers and other important stakeholders.

Methodology

The study is a quantitative research in which Descriptive survey design was adopted shall be. The research was based on the perception of the respondents (team leaders and assistant in the college). on the effect of shared leadership on team effectiveness in the Higher Educational system, specifically at the Harvarde College of Science Business and Management Studies, Abeokuta, Ogun Sate, Nigera. The researcher used primary source of data collection. The population of the study comprised of all the administrative and academic staff of Harvarde College of Science Business and Management Studies, Abeokuta, Ogun Sate, Nigera. The samples of this research were 34 respondents; which consisted of the principal officers, administration heads, faculty heads, and departmental heads in Harvarde College of Science Business and Management Studies, Abeokuta, Ogun Sate, Nigera.. These respondents and the schools were selected using purposive sampling technique, a non-probability sampling technique. The respondents included the Provost, Deputy Provost, Registrar, Deputy Registrar, Bursar, School Administrator, Administrative Officers, Admission Officers, Examination and Record Officer, The Deans, and The Head of Departments.

This study shall make use of a modified adopted survey questionnaire to get the perception of team leaders and team members on the subject matter of this research. The adopted questionnaire shall be modified to suit the research hypotheses to be tested. The questionnaire shall collect demographic data of the respondents as well as their opinion on the subject matter, which shall be in accordance with the variables in the research topic. Due to proximity, the researcher used electronic mode to administer the questionnaire. The questionnaire was sent to the respondents via email. The questionnaire was designed and administered with the use of Monkey survey. The researcher first contacted the school Registrar, who later delegated to the school administrator. The researcher was able to collect the respondents email addresses through the school administrator. The questionnaire was sent to 34 respondents, out of which only 29 were completed and submitted. This made the return

rate 85.3% of the total respondents. The data collected from the respondents was sorted, coded, scored and analysed. Simple percentage was used to interpret the data on the questionnaire. The hypotheses were tested based on the analysis of the respondents' responses to the questions on the questionnaire.

Hypothesis 1: Shared leadership is not adopted.

Questions to examine shared leadership were asked and reported by respondents during the survey, these are reports of findings based one each question.

Table 1: My team members clearly understand the hierarchy/structure of the team

	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Agree (SA)	12	41.4
Agree (A)	14	48.3
Disagree (DA)	2	6.9
Strongly Disagree (SD)	1	3.4
Total	29	100.0

12 (41.4%) of the respondents strongly agreed to team members clearly understanding the hierarchy/structure of the team, 14 (48.3%) agreed, 2 (6.9%) disagreed while 1 (3.4%) strongly disagreed to their team members clearly understanding the hierarchy/structure of the team. Hence, most of the respondents agreed to the statement.

Hypothesis 2: There is no relationship between shared leadership and team effectiveness

Questions to examine the relationship between shared leadership and team effectiveness were asked and reported by respondents during the survey. These are reports of findings based one each question.

Table 2: My team is effective because....my team members clearly understand the hierarchy/structure of the team

	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Agree (SA)	15	53.6
Agree (A)	10	35.7
Disagree (DA)	2	7.1
Strongly Disagree (SD)	1	3.6
Total	28	100.0

Majority of the respondents agreed that their team is effective because their team members clearly understand the hierarchy/structure of the team.15 (53.6%) of the respondents strongly agreed to team members clearly understanding the hierarchy/structure of the team, 10 (35.7%) agreed, 2 (7.1%) disagreed while 1 (3.6%) strongly disagreed to their team members clearly understanding the hierarchy/structure of the team.

Hypothesis 3: There is no relationship between shared leadership and team trust

Questions to examine the relationship between shared leadership and team trust were asked and reported by respondents during the survey. These are reports of findings based one each question.

Table 3: There is trust in my team because.... my team members clearly understand the hierarchy/structure of the team

	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Agree (SA)	15	55.6
Agree (A)	8	29.6
Disagree (DA)	2	7.4
Strongly Disagree (SD)	2	7.4
Total	27	100.0

Majority of the respondents agreed that there is trust in their team because my team members clearly understand the hierarchy/structure of the team. 15 (55.6%) of the respondent strongly agreed to team members clearly understanding the hierarchy/structure of the team, 8 (29.6%) agreed, while 2 (7.4%) respectively disagreed and strongly disagreed to their team members clearly understanding the hierarchy/structure of the team.

Discussion on Findings

Hypothesis One states that Shared leadership is not adopted Harvarde College of Science Business and Management Studies, Abeokuta, Ogun State, Nigeria. The area of study of this research was Harvarde College of Science Business and Management Studies, Ogun State, Nigeria. The structure of the college has various departments(teams), both in the academic and administrative units of the school. The academic unit has four broad teams, which are the schools under which the smaller teams are. The smaller teams are the departments. The schools are headed by Deans, while the departments are headed by the Heads of Departments (H.O.D.). The responses of the respondents, which comprised of 20 team leaders, 9 assistant team leaders (see 4.1.1), showed that over 70% of the team leaders adopted shared leadership. The responses of the respondents as analysed in 4.2.1 to 4.2.10, clearly shows that shared leadership is adopted in the administration of the college, especially at the top management level.

Hypothesis 2, there is no relationship between shared leadership and team effectiveness. Shared leadership is praised as a method that improves performance and has applicability in many management disciplines, including educational management. This study demonstrates a strong link between effective team leadership and shard performance. The 29 respondents' replies unmistakably demonstrate that shared leadership is related with better team task performance. Through the use of team assets including the knowledge and skills of group members, shared leadership increases the social capital of the team, which in turn promotes team performance. The conclusion of this study also explains why group members provide more of their own and the organization's resources to the task at hand, share more information, and feel more committed when they take on leadership roles for others and the group's mission or purpose. When members of a project team are more willing to take on mutual leadership roles and actively participate in positive communication and decision-making, it enables people to provide more resources, share more information, and demonstrate higher levels of commitment. These effects taken as a whole would boost team productivity.

Hypothesis three, there is no relationship between shared leadership and team trust. This study demonstrates unequivocally that shared leadership and team trust are significantly correlated. This simply means that trust is fostered among team members when shared leadership is properly

utilised in a school system. Within a department, faculty, college, or even the administrative entity, this is possible. Teamwork is enhanced when group members are inspired by one another because there is a high level of respect and trust among them. For a number of reasons, shared leadership should be closely tied to team members' trust in their virtual team.

Conclusion

The results of this study clearly demonstrate that shared leadership improves organisational performance as a whole. In recent years, it has become more and more obvious that the traditional top-down model of leadership needs to be expanded upon. While there is growing interest in the shared leadership area, studies focusing on school teams are still scarce, it was found during the course of this study. Shared Leadership in Teams and its Impact on Team Effectiveness When team members provide their leadership to others and to the objective or purpose of their team, they feel higher dedication, bringing in greater personal and organisational resources to bear on difficult tasks, and sharing more. When team members interact, exchange ideas, and help one another through difficult situations, they grow to trust and respect one another, which becomes a further asset for enhancing team performance. The association between shared leadership and team effectiveness is well established in this study, and other factors like member proximity and team diversity act as moderators. Shared leadership fosters and promotes individual initiative, which has a good impact on how a firm runs. The current study provides insight into the question of whether shared leadership is positively correlated with team performance by merging ideas from shared leadership, team effectiveness, and school administration.

Recommendations

Based on the outcome of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Team leaders should define and communicate the team vision with the team members.
2. Team leaders should encourage recognition in their team
3. Team Leaders should ensure they speak to their team members from the heart
4. Team leaders should delegate responsibilities to their team members and also empower them.
5. Team leaders should commit to continued coaching, training and education

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